

Does usual function definition apply to empty sets?

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Abstract

Applying the usual function definition to two empty sets gives a contradiction regarding "set elements". But a simple specification could solve the issue.

Introduction

Empty-function existence would be ensured by the absence of elements, in the empty sets, which could deny the function itself; it is said vacuously true. In fact in classical logic not-false or not-not-true implies true. But it isn't the case in intuitionistic logic. Nevertheless here we show the inapplicability of usual function definition to empty sets in classical logic too.

Function definition: a relation f is a function if for each $x \in X$ there exists a unique $y \in Y$ such that $(x, y) \in f$ ($f : X \rightarrow Y$) [1] [2] [3] [4] [5]. x and y are elements in the sets.

We see that, in general: **"pairs of elements constitute a function"**.

Taking two empty sets, domain and codomain, we see that: **"pairs of elements don't constitute an empty-function"**, because there aren't elements by empty-set definition. This is clearly contradictory compared to the function general definition; empty-function isn't a function.

Anyway there is a deeper level, but more subtle, due to applying the term "element" of the definition to an empty set. The application would start equating an "element" with a "not-element" (or not-existing element), then a contradiction; the definition says "for each element" and not "for each not-element". Considering a practical case, for example $x = \text{"an odd number divisible by 2"}$, x may look like an element because it is defined by a proposition, but only at first glance. $x \in \text{empty-set}$ only if it is a not-element.

So, usual function definition doesn't apply to empty sets.

Can the issue be solved specifying x and y aren't necessarily set elements? Is this specification possible?

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References

- [1] Robert André. *Set Theory: An Introduction to Axiomatic Reasoning*. CRC Press, 2025.
- [2] Herbert B Enderton. *Elements of set theory*. Gulf Professional Publishing, 1977.
- [3] Paul R Halmos. *Naive set theory*, 1974.
- [4] math.purdue. <https://www.math.purdue.edu/~arapura/algebra/appendix.pdf>.
- [5] Charles C Pinter. *A book of set theory*. Courier Corporation, 2014.